

9.1 Guidelines for GEP Design Evaluation

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Information in this report that may influence other GEARING ROLES tasks

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All	Design and Implementation of GEPs

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GEARING ROLES project

GEARING-Roles is a four-year Coordination and Support Action project that will bring together a pan-European group of academics and industry professionals to collaborate and exchange knowledge, good practices, and lessons learned on designing, implementing, and evaluating 6 Gender Equality Plans (GEPs). The project, therefore, has a firm objective of challenging and transforming gender roles and identities linked to professional careers, and work towards real institutional change. This multi-disciplinary, multi-national, and multi-sectorial collaboration will be supported by training in this space, mentoring activities, awareness-raising campaigns as well as bi-annual videos and podcasts and annual networking events.

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List of Abbreviations

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- EIGE European Institute for Gender Equality
- GEP Gender Equality Plan
- KPI Key Performance Indicator
- WP Work Packages

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Executive Summary:

This document serves as the main guidelines for the evaluation of the GEARING ROLES project (Grant Agreement Nr.: 824536), to be used during the whole implementation period. It describes the rationale and the details of the Design Evaluation (9.1).

1. Introduction ¹

As a project, GEARING-Roles sets out to make substantial progress in realising gender equality in academic institutions in Europe. GEARING-Roles' main objective is the promotion and realisation of structural change and gender equality in academia and research (Swafs 09-2018: 3). The core element for realising this objective is the GEP - Gender Equality Plan – that each of GEARING-Roles' six implementing institutions will design and implement. These GEPs will be designed combining context specific information with a common reference tool, the GEAR tool developed by EIGE (<https://eige.europa.eu/gender-mainstreaming/toolkits/gear>). The GEPs are designed and developed to tailor fit the respective institution's needs and requirements, leading to a coherent and integrated design logic, building on the GEAR toolkit.

This deliverable will establish and describe the evaluation measures to be used by the Work Package 9 leaders of evaluation and assessment, based at Radboud University Nijmegen. The evaluators recognise and acknowledge that the GEP implementation process may be subjected to various changes, challenges, and adaptations throughout its duration. The guidelines in this deliverable thus aim to include attention for such adaptations and changes, anticipating challenges that implementing partners may meet, and address them either directly, or offer tools to mitigate or solve them.

Problem analysis and diagnosis:

The GEPs will be developed by the six implementing partners to promote and realise structural change and gender equality in academia and research. As the primary goal, this includes improving the position of women in academia and research and offering remedial strategies to challenge visible and invisible practices and biases which form obstacles to personal career and research development in academia and research. In order to ensure that the GEPs reach the goals of structural change and gender equality through a successful implementation, and maintain a stronghold in academic and organisational hierarchies beyond the implementation term, an effective evaluation and measurement tool has been developed. The evaluation guidelines developed by Work Package 9 will contribute to the development and implementation of both existing and future gender equality tools.

To successfully challenge traditional gender roles, including women's unequal work representation and the gendered hierarchy within academia, Key Performance Indicators², as described in Swafs 09-2018, will serve to evaluate the implementing partners in their implementation of the GEPs by highlighting objectives to meet throughout, and by the end of its four year run. While the proposal sets a clear number of KPIs to be met by the end of the implementation term, the applicability and feasibility of the

¹ This text is similar for the Deliverables 9.1, 9.2, and 9.3 because they share a common introduction, and a common goal: the evaluation of the GEPs designed and implemented by six GEARING-Roles consortium members.

² Hereafter referred to as KPIs.

KPIs at each implementing partner must be taken into consideration. Positioning and assessing the achievement of the KPIs aims to support the development of an integrated GEP design logic (Swafs 09-2018: 38) which utilises evaluation and assessment indicators to measure if the GEP is an effective tool to challenge deeply entrenched notions on gender roles and identities, and shift approaches to workplace equality.

GEAR goals and objectives:

Following the Swafs 09-2018 (p3-5) proposal, individual GEPs have as their goal the fulfilment and achievement of four main objectives, as explained below:

- a) Female career progression: to remove all barriers that may impede a woman's career path and subsequent success.
- b) Leadership and decision making: to address gender imbalances in the representation, processes, and the promotion of women leadership in research institutions.
- c) Education and research: to promote gender mainstreaming in research (especially in STEM), by including a gender perspective in research programmes, and supporting women's scientific careers.
- d) Promotion of gender equality in research organisations and reinforcing the European Research area (ERA): to disseminate frameworks and institutional gender assessments and evaluation strategies to establish commitment to gender equality in European organisations, and build sustainable long-term gender equality networks.

Key performance indicators as set in the project proposal:

The Gender Equality Plan Goals and Objectives will be measured with an agreed upon set of KPIs. These KPIs link to the four objectives of the GEARING-Roles project.

For the first expected impact, namely an increase in the participation of women in research and innovation, and improvement of their careers prospects, the KPIs are:

- (1) 60 female researchers participating in mentoring programmes.
- (2) 100 participatory Career Development Plans completed.
- (3) Transfer of good practice in HR recruitment processes: at least 12 lessons learnt and shared, 6 examples of good practice adopted by the other institutions.

For the second expected impact, which is an improvement of the gender balance in decision-making bodies in research, the KPIs are:

- (1) 10% increase in the representation of women in decision making bodies in relation with baseline assessment at different ranks.
- (2) 6 action plans developed with elements to include leadership and female participation in decision making.

- (3) Data collection on increasing awareness.
- (4) Number of questionnaires contrasting data in relation to baseline assessment.

For the third expected impact, which is inclusion, where relevant, of the gender dimension in research content and an increase in the quality and societal relevance of produced knowledge, technologies and innovations, the KPIs are:

- (1) 75 people trained (sex disaggregated and ideally broken down to permanent and temporary staff).
- (2) 80% participation satisfaction with training (exit questionnaires).
- (3) Number of courses with gender training embedded.

For the fourth expected impact, which is that the implementation of Gender Equality Plans in the medium to long term will contribute to the achievement of the ERA, the KPIs are:

- (1) 1 training course on the gender dimensions of research per year.
- (2) An increase in the number of researchers working on gender issues.
- (3) Number of projects awarded addressing gender topics.
- (4) Number of dissertations and master theses finished addressing gender topics, and/or in which gender dimensions and women as users are explicitly taken into account.
- (5) Percentage of increase in different disciplines of the underrepresented genders.
- (6) Percentage of increase of the number of female young researchers (grant holders) to the total per each scientific discipline with respect to year 0 of the project.
- (7) Percentage of increase of the number of female researchers to the total per each scientific discipline with respect to year 0 of the project.

A guide to measuring and evaluating the GEP implementation:

The following guidelines are developed by Work Package 9 leaders to help evaluate the design and impact of each implementing partner's GEP, and to refine and contextualise KPIs for their potential to contribute to a successful implementation of GEPs. The guidelines will ensure the continued quality of internal assessment mechanisms to evaluate the GEPs, and will aid in an analysis of the GEPs as key to addressing gender inequality among consortium partners. The report has been divided into three sections, each of which will deal with a specific aspect of the GEP implementation, leading to a coherent and logical strategic plan.

2. Guidelines for Design Evaluation

The GEP design objectives:

The design evaluation will seek to establish the logic and consistency between the GEP's policy instruments and the objectives it aims to meet. To this end the design evaluation, following Swafs 09-2018 (p17-18), will be utilised in the early phase of the project to identify the potential achievement of the four main objectives, as well as to assess the GEP's potential to reach shifts in the organisational and institutional culture and behaviours of the respective academic institutions. These main objectives aim at bringing about structural change and gender equality in research institutions, and to ensure the success of this goal both an *ex ante* and *ex post*³ evaluation is required. The *ex ante* evaluation will determine:

- a) Respective to each partner institution, the accumulation of data on which inherent practices and protocols are seen as forming the major obstacles to gender equality.
- b) Which measures for implementing and ensuring gender equality, as formulated in the GEP, are already implemented at the implementing partner institutions?
- c) Which new measures to be implemented have been developed in the GEP of each implementing partner?
- d) To which degree these measures relate to the aims of GEARING-Roles and overarching objectives of the GEP, taking into account the contextual factors of each partner institution.
- e) To which degree it is expected that these measures will be able to achieve the KPIs and lead to structural or incremental change regarding gender equality at an academic and organisational level. This will include an in-depth analysis of the relevant numbers and percentages which reflect the gendered nature of each research institution.

Criteria to measure design objectives:

The criteria discussed below may be evaluated objectively, referring to the potential to achieve change at an organisational level, while a subjective evaluation will scrutinise the satisfaction of, and consensus between the change agents and the potential beneficiaries of the GEPs with the design of the GEP.

- a) Feasibility: is the GEP implementation feasible within the conditions set by the GEARING-Roles project? These conditions include the timeline, as well as the financial, human resource, and infrastructure conditions.
- b) Consistency: are the instruments foreseen in the GEP consistent with the goals, objectives, and key performance indicators of the GEARING-Roles project? If applicable, which changes and adaptations are made by partner institutions and how do these changes relate to the goals and objectives of the project and potentially affect its implementation?
- c) Coordination: this refers to the manner in which the various tasks have been allocated within the GEP, which can be assessed using the following criteria: upholding any agreements decided

³ For more information on the *ex post* evaluation, please refer to D9.2 Guidelines for the GEP Impact Evaluation.

upon by the consortium; the coordination of tasks; the division of tasks; and the efforts necessary to reach the goals and objectives within the proposed timeline.

As a result of the coordination and cooperation between Work Packages, efficient and coordinated efforts to bring about structural change and gender equality in research institutions are strengthened by maintaining a structured implementation strategy. To further these efforts, space is granted to all implementation partners to carefully map any discrepancies and adaptation processes during the GEP implementation, which will be taken into account by Work Package 9 during the evaluation.

